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Physiochemical and Potentially Toxic Elements (PTEs) Level in Water Resources: A Study of Selected Communities in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Water contamination/pollution is one of the challenges faced by the developing countries in which Nigeria is included. This study focuses on the evaluation of physiochemical and potentially toxic elements (PTEs) level in water resources from selected communities in Abeokuta, Nigeria. Water samples from water resources (hand-dug wells, rivers and taps) within the selected seven (7) communities was collected. All water parameters were carried out using standard laboratory procedure. The results revealed that pH in Lisa well (5.94), Ilaru river (5.91), Kanga well (5.73) and Agodo river (5.39) were above the WHO standard (6.5-8.5) while DO in Efuye river (4.95 mg/L), Ilaru river (3.25 mg/L) and Agodo river (3.40 mg/L) were not in line with the WHO standard (5.0). Furthermore, the concentration of Pb in Efuye river and Asipa well (0.016 mg/L) was above the WHO standard (0.01 mg/L) while Cd and Hg in all the water sources were above the WHO standard (0.003 and 0.006 mg/L) respectively. In conclusion, the study revealed that the some of the water sources are polluted with PTEs such as Pb, while all are polluted with Cd and Hg. Therefore, the is unsuitable for use and detrimental to environmental and human health.

Keywords: Physiochemical parameters, toxic elements, toxicological risk and water source

1. INTRODUCTION

The presence of potentially toxic elements (PTEs) in water sources poses significant environmental and public health challenges (Dey *et al.*, 2021). These elements, which include heavy metals such as lead, arsenic, cadmium, and mercury, are often introduced into aquatic ecosystems through industrial discharges, agricultural runoff, and urban pollution (Umoren *et al.*, 2024).

Li *et al.* (2018) and Hossain and Chowdhury (2020) reported that understanding the physiochemical parameters and concentrations of PTEs in water sources is crucial for assessing their toxicological risks and implementing effective management strategies. Furthermore, physiochemical parameters, such as pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen, and electrical conductivity, significantly influence the behavior and bioavailability of PTEs in aquatic environments (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023; Umoren *et al.*, 2025). Adams and Dang (2019), reported that the solubility of heavy metals can vary with changes in pH; at lower pH levels, the solubility increases, enhancing the potential for toxic exposure to aquatic organisms and, subsequently, to humans through bioaccumulation in the food chain.

Regulatory bodies, such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), have established guidelines and permissible limits for various PTEs to safeguard public health (WHO, 2024). In the selected communities, the people in those communities depend heavily on the water sources for domestic use such as cooking, bathing, washing and other basic water usage. Therefore, the risks involved in the usage of highly toxic water can have adverse effects on health (Patil *et al.*, 2012; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, high temperatures can accelerate chemical reactions that may release PTEs from sediments, leading to increased concentrations in the water column (Martínez-Hernández *et al.*, 2020).

Chronic exposure to elevated concentrations of PTEs can result in severe health implications, including neurological, renal, and developmental disorders. The risk is particularly pronounced for vulnerable populations, such as children and pregnant women, who are more susceptible to the harmful effects of these elements (United Nations, 2014; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023 & 2025). The above stated concerns require an academic effort to provide solutions and mitigation efforts against the risks of being exposed to highly toxic water sources within the selected communities in Abeokuta, Ogun State.

As pointed out by Ephraim *et al.* (2021) the results from the research will play a vital role in influencing regulations and policies related to WHO water quality standards and by extension, the whole country. Therefore, the study will provide the evidence needed to advocate for and recommend changes in regulations to protect public health and the environment.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

Abeokuta is situated between latitudes coordinates 7°9'39"N and 3°20'54"E. Its estimated area covers 40.63 km². Located in the Nigerian rainforest, Abeokuta is positioned atop a basement complex of volcanic rocks, which are covered by some layers of sedimentary strata (APPENDIX: Plates 1-7). Due to the constant increase in the human population, the amount of solid waste in Abeokuta is on the rise. Approximately 50% of the solid waste generated daily

in Abeokuta is collected by the Ogun State Environmental Protection Agency, concerned citizens, and private waste management firms. Solid waste is discarded throughout the city's streets, with an estimated production rate of 0.60 kg per person per day.

The other 50% is either buried, incinerated, or disposed of in any available land area, as well as being thrown into lagoons, streams, and drainage systems (Ojo *et al.*, 2023; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2025).

2. 2. Sampling Procedure

Seven (7) water samples were taken from water sources (hand-dug wells, river) in selected communities in Abeokuta, Ogun state, Nigeria using a pre-treated (5% Nitric acid overnight) 1L plastic container. All sampling collections were meticulously recorded with a pen and field notebook, then all samples were brought to the laboratory for examination with meticulous labelling.

2. 3. Physicochemical Analysis

The physicochemical quality of the water samples was assessed, focusing on parameters such as pH, temperature, total dissolved solids, electrical conductivity, turbidity, total hardness, and chloride. Standard methods were utilized for these assessments (AOAC, 2019).

The pH of the samples was measured using a pH meter (electrometric method), with measurements taken in situ. The equipment was standardized using buffer solutions with known concentration before recording the pH values of the water samples. Total dissolved solids and electrical conductivity were determined using a digital water quality meter. Turbidity was measured with a turbidity meter.

Total hardness was assessed using an EDTA titrimetric method, with Eriochrome Black T serving as the indicator. Chloride levels were measured using the mercuric nitrate colorimetric method, utilizing potassium chromate as an indicator. Sulfate was analyzed gravimetrically with barium chloride acting as a precipitating agent.

2. 4. Potentially toxic element (PTE) Analysis

The water sample (10 cm³) was measured using a measuring cylinder. The sample was poured into a 250 cm³ of sterilized conical flask and treated with 20 cm³ of concentrated Nitric acid (HNO₃). The mixture was placed on a hot plate at 90 °C in a fume cupboard until a clear solution was achieved. The flask was allowed to cool to ambient temperature, then the digest was then filtered with Whatman No. 42 filter paper and diluted up to mark with deionized water in a 250 cm³ standard volumetric flask (AOAC, 2019), then PTEs were estimated using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy.

3. RESULTS

The summary of the statistics of the results obtained for the Physicochemical Parameters of water sources across the selected communities with WHO (2017) standards is shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the concentration of potentially toxic element (PTEs) in water sources across the selected communities with WHO (2017) standards is shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Physicochemical Parameters of water resources.
 Bold values in italics are not in line with the WHO standards.

Parameters	Efuye River	Lisa Well	Ilaru River	Kanga Well	Agodo River	Dangbogboru River	Asipa Well	WHO (2017)
pH	6.88	5.94	5.91	5.73	5.39	6.31	6.96	6.5-8.5
TDS (mg/L)	45.5	111.5	14	19	13	8.0	77	500
EC (μ S/cm)	91	223	29	39	27	17	155	1000
Salinity (mg/L)	45.5	111.5	14	19	12.5	8.0	77	100
T. Acidity (mg/L)	105	107	144.5	55	88.5	94	135	-
T. Alkalinity (mg/L)	40	51.5	26.5	9	18	23	55	200
Hardness (mg/L)	94.0	50.0	32.0	8.0	24.0	78.0	36.0	500
DO (mg/L)	4.95	5.65	3.25	5.60	3.40	5.55	4.60	> 5 (river) / < 2 (well)
BOD (mg/L)	1.35	1.50	0.60	0.35	0.90	0.10	2.70	20

Table 2. Concentration of Ionic and PTE (mg/L) in water sources.
 Bold values in italics are not in line with the WHO standards.

Location	NO ₃	PO ₄	SO ₄	Na	K	Pb	Cu	Cd	As	Ti	Hg
Efuye River	2.189	1.004	8.916	14.112	8.813	0.016	0.831	0.368	0.008	2.671	0.986
Lisa Well	1.932	0.932	8.236	14.832	8.902	0.011	0.736	0.416	0.011	3.102	1.023
Ilaru River	2.063	1.036	7.891	15.168	9.864	0.014	0.811	0.384	0.009	2.138	0.911
Kanga Well	2.456	1.012	8.121	14.364	9.023	0.011	0.833	0.391	0.01	2.481	0.937
Agodo River	2.241	0.986	7.936	15.022	9.366	0.01	0.728	0.423	0.014	2.935	1.081
Dangbogboru River	1.893	0.962	8.118	14.926	9.106	0.012	0.852	0.048	0.006	3.186	1.062
Asipa Well	1.911	1.049	7.912	15.482	10.021	0.016	0.708	0.433	0.012	3.012	0.945
WHO (2017)	50	-	250	200	-	0.01	2.00	0.003	0.01	-	0.006

4. DISCUSSIONS

4. 1. Physicochemical Parameters

The pH values for the water sources ranged from 5.39 – 6.96. The lowest pH was recorded in Agodo river (5.39) while the highest pH was recorded in Asipa well (6.96). All pH values except Efuye River and Asipa well does not comply with the WHO (2017) standard (6.5 - 8.5). Water with a pH below 8 is preferable for effective disinfection with chlorine, but lower pH levels can be corrosive. According to the research conducted by Zulum *et al.* (2016) and Abubakar *et al.* (2018) in Maiduguri indicate that the majority of borehole water in Maiduguri fall within the acceptable limits. The TDS value in the water sources ranged from 8.0 – 111.5 mg/L. The lowest TDS was recorded in Dangbogboru river (8.0 mg/L) while the TDS was recorded in Lisa well (111.5 mg/L). All TDS values were in compliance with WHO (2017) standard (500 mg/L).

A comparable investigation conducted in Kyarimi, Gwange, Shehuri, Bulumkutu, and Bolori areas of Maiduguri reveals that the TDS level ranges from 85 to 121 mg/L (Abubakar *et al.*, 2018). The EC ranged from 17- 223 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The lowest EC was recorded in Dangbogboru river (17 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) while the highest EC was recorded in Lisa well (223 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). All EC values were in compliance with WHO (2017) standard (1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). The EC concentration from the streams is lower than the report in effluents from Omu-Aran, Nigeria (432 – 547 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) (Elemile *et al.*, 2019) but extremely lower than the report from industrial effluent in Imo State, Nigeria (10460 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) (Ogemdi and Gold, 2018). Salinity values ranged from 8 – 111.5 mg/L.

The lowest Salinity was recorded in Dangbogboru River (8.0 mg/L) while the Salinity was recorded in Lisa well (111.5 mg/L). All Salinity value except Lisa River were in compliance with WHO (2017) standard (100 mg/L). The salinity recorded from this study are extremely higher than that reported from mini Whuo Stream (24.82 \pm 4.97 mg/L), Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria (Edori *et al.*, 2021). Total acidity ranged from 55 – 144.5 mg/L. The lowest total acidity was recorded in Kanga well (55 mg/L) while the highest was recorded in Ilaru River (144.5 mg/L). Total Alkalinity ranged from 9 – 55 mg/L. The Total acidity recorded across the streams is exponentially higher than the report from Asa River, Ilorin (26.3 – 50.23 mg/L) (Olawale, 2016) and River Sokoto (05 – 20 mg/L) (Raji *et al.*, 2015). The lowest alkalinity was recorded in Kanga well (9 mg/L) while the highest alkalinity was recorded in Asipa well (55 mg/L). All alkalinity values were in compliance with WHO (2017) standard (200 mg/L). Hardness ranged from 8 – 94 mg/L. The high total alkalinity recorded in station C can be linked to temperature and increased levels of bicarbonate because of the high rate of photosynthesis (Eze and Chigbu, 2015). The lowest hardness value was recorded in Kanga well (8 mg/L) while the highest hardness value was recorded in Efuye River (94 mg/L). All hardness values were in WHO (2017) standard (500 mg/L). The DO in the water sources ranged from 3.25 – 5.65 mg/L. The lowest DO was recorded in Ilaru River (3.25 mg/L) while the highest was recorded in Lisa well (5.65 mg/L). All DO values except Lisa well, Kanga well and dangbogboru river were in compliance with WHO (2017) standard (>5 mg/L). The DO concentration across the water sources is higher than the report from industrial effluent at 100 meters downstream of River Iju (7.56 mg/L) (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023) and abattoir effluent in Omu – Aran, Nigeria (5.80 – 7.23 mg/L) (Elemile *et al.*, 2019). The BOD in water sources ranged from 0.1 – 2.7 mg/L. The lowest BOD was recorded in Dangbogboru river (0.1 mg/L) while the highest BOD was recorded in Asipa well (2.7 mg/L). All BOD values were in compliance with WHO (2017) standard (20 mg/L).

4. 2. Ionic and Potentially Toxic Element Level

The concentration of NO₃ ranged from 1893 – 2456 mg/L. The lowest NO₃ value was recorded in Dangbogboru river (1893 mg/L) while the highest NO₃ was recorded in Kanga river (2456 mg/L). All NO₃ concentrations were in compliance with the WHO (2017) standard (50 mg/L). The PO₄ ranged from 0.932 – 1.049 mg/L. The lowest PO₄ was recorded in Dangbogboru river (0.932) while the highest PO₄ was recorded in Asipa well. SO₄ ranged from 7891 – 8916 mg/L. The lowest SO₄ was recorded in Ilaru river (7891 mg/L) while the highest SO₄ was recorded in Efuye river (8916 mg/L). All SO₄ concentrations were within the WHO (2017) standard (250 mg/L).

The Na ranged from 14.1 – 15.5 mg/L. The lowest Na was recorded in Efuye river (14.1 mg/L) while the highest Na was recorded in Asipa well (15.5 mg/L). All Na concentrations were in line with the WHO (2017) standard (200 mg/L). Sodium concentrations in the surface waters of the N'djili basin ranged from 32.82 mg/L to 98.09 mg/L, with an average of 54.52 mg/L. The highest Na concentrations were found in the waters of Rivière N'djili and Rivière Ngwele, measuring 98.1 and 64.5 mg/L, respectively. Potassium ranged from 8.81 – 9.86 mg/L. The lowest K was recorded in Efuye river (8.81 mg/L) while the highest K was recorded in Ilaru river (9.86 mg/L).

Potassium levels across the various surface water sampling points in the N'djili basin varied from 18.59 to 55.57 mg/L, with an average of 33.4 mg/L. Notably, the N'djili and Ngwele rivers recorded significant potassium concentrations at 55.57 and 22.93 mg/L, respectively. The Lukaya, Matete, and Masina rivers displayed lower potassium levels at 18.59, 20.77 and 22.93 mg/L, respectively (Nzomba, 2024).

The concentration of Pb was ranged from 0.01 – 0.016 mg/L. The lowest Pb was recorded in Agodo river (0.01 mg/L) while the highest Pb was recorded in Efuye river and Asipa well (0.016 mg/L). All Pb concentrations except Asipa well and Efuye river were in line with WHO (2017) standard (0.01 mg/L). Lead concentrations were 0.063 mg/L in the Lukaya River, 0.081 mg/L in the Matete River (the highest recorded), 0.058 mg/L in the N'djili River (the lowest recorded), 0.061 mg/L in the Ntshuenge River, and 0.065 mg/L in the Ngwele River (Nzomba, 2024). Lead has been recognized for centuries as a cumulative general metabolic poison (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2017). A prolonged exposure to Pb can permanent damage to the central nervous system and kidney (Aluko *et al.*, 2024).

The concentration of Cu ranged from 0.708 – 0.852 mg/L. The lowest Cu was recorded in Asipa well (0.708 mg/L) while the highest Cu was recorded in Dangbogboru river (0.852 mg/L). All Cu concentrations were within the WHO (2017) standard (2.00 mg/L). Copper is an element that is an important component of various enzymes and it plays a significant role in the production of melanin, free radical elimination, iron utilization, etc. However, excessive consumption of copper can cause diarrhoea, vomiting, liver damage, nausea, and abdominal pain (Ulla *et al.*, 2012). The concentration of Cd ranged from 0.048 – 0.433 mg/L. The lowest Cd was recorded in Dangbogboru river (0.048 mg/L) while the highest was recorded in Asipa river (0.433 mg/L). All Cd concentrations were above the WHO (2017) standard (0.003 mg/L).

The highest cadmium concentration was 0.013 mg/L in the Matete River, while the lowest was 0.003 mg/L in the Lukaya River. The higher Cd values corroborated with the reports of Kieri *et al.* (2021) in Silver River, Bayelsa State, and Anyanwu *et al.* (2023) in Ikwu River, Umuahia, Nigeria attributed to anthropogenic input.

A prolonged exposure to high Cd Concentration can result in health conditions such as pulmonary and nephrological conditions (WHO (2017), 2011; Aluko *et al.*, 2024).

Arsenic (As) ranged from 0.006 – 0.014 mg/L. The lowest As was recorded in Dangbogboru river (0.006 mg/L) while the highest Cd was recorded in Agodo river (0.014 mg/L). All arsenic concentrations in the water sources were within the WHO (2017) standard (0.01 mg/L). Arsenic is one of the non-essential heavy metals found in the environment, its concentration in ingestible items suggests contamination. However, arsenic has been reported in potable water resources in Nigeria (Izah and Srivastav, 2015). The concentration of Ti ranged from 2.138 – 3.186 mg/L. The lowest Ti was recorded in Ilaru river (2.138 mg/L) while the highest Ti was recorded in Dangbogboru river (3.186 mg/L). The concentration of Hg ranged from 0.911 – 1.081 mg/L. The lowest Hg was recorded in Ilaru river (0.911 mg/L) while the highest Hg was recorded in Agodo river (1.081 mg/L). All Hg concentrations were above the WHO (2017) standard (0.006 mg/L).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Understanding the physicochemical parameters of water sources is crucial for assessing the risk of exposure to potentially toxic elements as well as the monitoring of these parameters can help in the prevention and remediation of contaminated water sources, thereby protecting public health and the environment. The study has evaluated the physiochemical parameters and potentially toxic element concentration in water sources in selected communities (Efuye, Lisa, Ilaru, Kanga, Agodo, Dangbogboru and Asipa) in Abeokuta, Ogun state Nigeria. The study revealed that some of the water resources has unacceptable pH and dissolved oxygen (DO), and are contaminated with Pb. Furthermore, all were contaminated with Cd and Hg making it unsuitable for use and detrimental to environmental and human health.

Recommendations

The following set of recommendations are given based on the study

- ✓ The government or local authorities should provide information to the population about the risks associated with water contamination and encourage safe water consumption practices.
- ✓ The government or local authorities should provide remediation practices to the contaminated water sources

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**APPENDIX
IMAGES OF THE WATER RESOURCES**

Plate 1. Efuye River.

Plate 2. Lisa Well.

Plate 3. Ilaru River.

Plate 4. Kanga Well.

Plate 5. Agodo River.

Plate 6. Dangbogboru River.

Plate 7. Asipa Well.